

THE MAIN PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF COLLABORATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. Collaborative problem solving involves two different constructs—collaboration and problem solving. The assumption is that collaboration for a group task is essential because some problem-solving tasks are too complex for an individual to work through alone or the solution will be improved from the joint capacities of a team. People vary in the information, expertise, and experiences that they can bring to bear in order to jointly solve a particular problem.

Keywords: Collaborative problem solving, team work, method, learning, education.

INTRODUCTION

The term “collaboration” has different meanings in different environments. In K-12, collaboration almost always means an individual task can be solved by anyone in the group, but collaboration is also an instructional strategy to enable learning more efficiently or effectively. In the world of work (industry, military), the term “collaborative” usually means a group task in which no one member of the group can solve the task alone.

MAIN PART

Generally, collaborative problem solving has two main areas: the collaborative (e.g., communication or social aspects) and the knowledge or cognitive aspects (e.g., domain-specific problem-solving strategies). These two areas are often referred to as “teamwork” and “taskwork.” The primary distinction between individual problem solving and collaborative problem solving is the social component in the context of a group task. This is composed of processes such as the need for communication, the exchange of ideas, and shared identification of the problem and its elements.

Within the PISA framework, three competencies form the core of the collaboration dimension: establishing and maintaining shared understanding, taking appropriate action to solve the problem, and establishing and

maintaining group organization. The framework also identifies four problem-solving processes: exploring and understanding, representing and formulating, planning and executing, and monitoring and reflecting.

In addition to the definition of collaborative problem solving, there are a number of issues associated with the design of an assessment of that competency. These include the following:

- What is the nature of the assessment task(s)? What content is to be assessed? Is the task illdefined or well-defined?
- Who is collaborating? Are they human-to-human or human-to-agent interactions? How many members are on the teams?
- What is the composition of the team? Is it homogeneous or heterogeneous? Do the team members assume similar or different roles?
- What is being evaluated? Is it individual or team outcomes? Is it process variables?

The human-to-human assessment approach is embedded in a less standardized assessment environment and offers a high level of face validity. A student collaborates with other students, so the behavior of both is difficult to control. Also, the success of one student depends on the behavior of the other student, as well as the stimuli and reactions that he/she offers. This has implications for scoring. How can the open conversation and large variety of stimuli be identified and utilized for scoring?

In the human-to-agent approach, the assessment environment is more standardized. The behavior of computer agents must be preprogrammed, so the response alternatives of the item to which the student reacts need to be limited to some extent and every possible response of the student needs to be attached to a specific response by the computer agents' stimuli or event in the problem scenario. Such an approach ensures that the situation is rather standardized, and furthermore enables comprehensive scoring techniques since every possible turn in collaboration is predefined. Nevertheless, the human-to-agent approach has the shortcoming of its artificial appearance and other conceptual questions, such as whether the CPS measured in this way can represent real-life collaborative problem solving.

The outcome data are collected through evaluative scoring throughout the process of collaboration. For example, an individual's actions during the collaboration can be scored as correct or incorrect by a human rater or an automatic scoring engine. The team-level outcome data are straightforward to collect. These data indicate whether a team solved the problem successfully.

There may be some process variables that are relatively easy to measure, such as the participation level of each team member and turn-taking. However, beyond these kinds of variables, interpreting actions and chats may be much more complex because of the dynamics and the sheer volume and complexity of data generated in log files.

Scoring collaborative problem-solving tasks is still very much in the research phase. More needs to be done before we can confidently make inferences about collaborative skills based on item responses. Outcome data (correct/incorrect/partially correct) can be analyzed with classical test

theory (reliability, correlations, biserial correlations), factor analysis, and item response theory (IRT). Process data may also be analyzed this way under specific circumstances and may also be analyzed using data mining tools and time series methods. It is important to note that the scoring model used is dependent on prior decisions about what should be measured and how. Assessment design and development must be undertaken in a way that aligns with the intended scoring model.

There are a number of issues NCEs must address in determining how to report results from a collaborative problem-solving assessment, including

- What will be reported: collaborative skill, problem-solving skill, or both? Will it be individual responses or team responses? Will it be within a content area or separately?
- What is the score structure: one scale or separate scales for sub-skills? Will the scores be reported using performance levels? Will the scores be mapped to sample items?

Despite these challenges, an assessment of collaborative problem solving The importance of collaborative problem solving as an educational outcome and important skill for life and work has continued to increase since the turn of the 21st century. Business continues to evolve requiring more cross-functional teams that work across international and cultural borders and possess complex cognitive, collaborative, and critical thinking skills (American Management Association, 2010). As Dede (2009) has observed.

The nature of collaboration is shifting to a more sophisticated skillset. In addition to collaborating face-to-face with colleagues across a conference table, 21st century workers increasingly accomplish tasks through mediated interactions with peers halfway across the world whom they may never meet face-to-face. ... Collaboration is worthy of inclusion as a 21st century skill

because the importance of cooperative interpersonal capabilities is higher and the skills involved are more sophisticated than in the prior industrial era.

CONCLUSION

Collaborative problem solving is a new assessment domain which is developing rapidly; however, there is much to be learned. The Assessment and Teaching of 21st Century Skills (ATC21S) CPS assessment has emerged out of a coalition of advisors and experts as part of a project sponsored by Microsoft, Intel, and Cisco, and part of a larger effort to define, develop pedagogies for, and assess 21st century skills (Griffin, 2014). Like PISA, tasks are designed to elicit collaborative problem-solving behaviors by having students work in pairs and communicate through on-screen chat messaging.

Unlike PISA, students are collaborating with other students rather than with computer agents. There is a clear delineation between social skills and cognitive skills. The ATC21S model emphasizes the development of both collaborative skills and the cognitive outcomes that can result from student mastery of those collaborative skills

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